

SafeHabitus

Deliverable D3.1

Farm safety in the EU: Which injuries, and who is counted?

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1. Executive Summary

What do the available tell us about the number of fatal and non-fatal injuries?

Data published by Eurostat indicate that, for the period 2012 – 2020, there were an average of 315 ± 36 fatal and $126\,817 \pm 16\,390$ non-fatal farm injuries annually. Over the ten-year period from 2012 to 2021, the incidence rate of non-fatal injuries in farming was 1 653 per 100 000 workers, whilst the incidence rate of fatal injuries was 4.1 fatalities per 100 000 workers. Though these estimates draw on the best available data, which were provided to Eurostat by the EU member states, these numbers are open to question.

What's the problem?

A systematic issue affecting the accuracy of farm injury data in Eurostat is the exclusion of self-employed and family workers' injury data from the official statistics that are used to monitor and evaluation the health and safety of farmers and farm workers. So, whilst Eurostat estimates that there are over 17 million people in the farm labour force comprising of self-employed farm holders, family members and employees, most EU countries only report data relating to employees. This leads to the exclusion of self-employed and family workers from most, though not all, Member States' occupation injuries reports.

Research Objectives

This report presents research that seeks to; improve understanding and awareness of farmer and farm worker health and safety; support the development of policy options that enhance policy and governance frameworks leading to improved working conditions in agriculture; and present case studies of the utility of comprehensive farm fatalities and injuries datasets. This task has two key objectives: 1) Extrapolate from farm injury and fatality data collected by Eurostat and national agencies to estimate the true number of farm Injuries and fatalities in member states, and 2) Demonstrate the use of high-quality health and safety data from two countries (Finland, Ireland) to national and EU farm health and safety policy makers and stakeholders.

Methods

Firstly, European Statistics on Accidents at Work (ESAW) reporting criteria pertaining to NACE Rev.2 industry subsector A01 Crop and animal production, hunting, and related service activities were examined to establish which workers and farm family members are included in national injury data that is reported to Eurostat. Secondly, a three-stage approach was used to estimate the number of farm fatalities and non-fatal injuries in the EU: 1) Member States with similar types of farms and farming practices were grouped together through cluster analysis, 2) Higher-quality injury data reported for one or more countries within each group were identified, and 3) The estimated occurrence of injuries and fatalities in the groups was extrapolated based on the high quality data. Finally, Case Studies were conducted in Finland and Ireland to examine farm injury and fatality data collection and its use in promoting farm health and safety policies and practices.

Results

Applying the methods outlined above, it is estimated that the true level of annual fatal and non-fatal injuries are, respectively, 545/100 000 and 206 000/100 000 workers. These estimates increase the number of reported fatal incidents by a factor of 1.7 and non-fatal injuries by 1.6. While this estimation provides a closer approximation to the real situation, it also indicates that a significant amount of injuries data is missing from the data reported to Eurostat. This missing data represents lost opportunities to understand the magnitude of the risk, learn from injuries, and

apply that knowledge to prevent future injuries. The current reporting downplays the real situation faced by farmers and farm workers by underestimating the true scale of farm-related injuries and fatalities. The advantages of having comprehensive data have been demonstrated by two case studies of Finland and Ireland. These showcase the potential benefits of robust data collection and reporting systems.

Recommendations

- **Recommendation 1 - DG AGRI:** Given the critical absence of reliable data to support policy making, we recommend that questions are included in the EU Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN), the EU Farm Structures Survey, and the EU Agriculture Census to identify the number of non-fatal injuries on farms. Each dataset has a unique set of strengths that, when combined, will provide a comprehensive overview of the level of
- **Recommendation 2 - DG AGRI:** We recommend that DG AGRI request, as part of the work planning process for the European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions (Eurofound):
 - The inclusion of questions in the European Working Conditions Surveys (EWCS) that enable the prevalence of occupational injury and ill health, and social sustainability of farming, to be estimated.
 - A special report is published by Eurofound following each EWCS documenting the working conditions of farmers and farm workers and assessing trends over time.
- **Recommendation 3 - DG AGRI:** The analysis of the data provided by the 11 SafeHabitus partners demonstrates that having a social insurance system that provides accident/injury insurance (compensation) for self-employed farmers and family members, in addition to employed workers, is closely associated with the availability of high-quality farm accident data. We recommend that DG AGRI undertake a study to explore the current coverage of farmers, family workers and employees by national social security/protection programmes and assess the feasibility of extending comprehensive occupational injury insurance coverage to self-employed farmers in Member States.
- **Recommendation 4 - Eurostat:** It is recommended that, based on the findings of this study, member states be required to provide data estimating the number of fatal and non-fatal injuries related to farming. It is recognised that this process will take time as it will require legislative changes at the EU level.
- **Recommendation 5 - DG EMPL:** That a working group of the Senior Labour Inspectors Committee (SLIC) be established to focus on improving occupational health and safety of farmers and farm workers. The purpose of the committee will be to:
 - Request regular updates on the number of fatal and non-fatal occupational injuries affecting farmers, family workers and employees.
 - Define common principles of labour inspection in the field of health and safety at work in agriculture and develop methods of assessing the national systems of inspection in relation to those principles.
 - Promote improved knowledge and mutual understanding of the different national systems and practices of labour inspection, the methods and legal frameworks for action.
 - Develop a reliable and efficient system of rapid information exchange between labour inspectorates about health and safety issues in agriculture.
 - Give its opinion on all matters relating to the enforcement by the Member States of EU legislation on health and safety at work in agriculture.
 - Study the possible impact of other Community policies on labour inspection activities relating to health and safety at work and working conditions in agriculture.

2. Background

2.1 Background and Context

Farming, classified under NACE Rev.2 subsector A01 Crop and animal production, hunting, and related service activities, constitutes a unique economic sector where the labour force comprises both salaried and non-salaried workers. As the majority (89.1%), of farm labour force on EU's 9.1 million farms comprises self-employed farmers and family labour, the presence of differing numbers for the farm labour force is not surprising. The EU Labour Force Survey indicates that 7.8 million people worked on EU farms in 2020, while the corresponding number in National Accounts Employment Data suggests 8.7 million employed people on EU farms. Meanwhile, the regular agricultural labour force (which also includes free labour) was reported as 17.2 million workers according to the 2020 Agricultural Census. However, the European Statistics on Accidents at Work (ESAW) reference population, reflecting the number of people at risk of experiencing agricultural occupational accidents, is lower than any of the numbers mentioned above - at 6.6 million workers in 2020. This clearly indicates that the current accident data collection systems do not cover all workers in EU farms, likely resulting in underestimated numbers of accidents.

According to the European Statistics on Accidents at Work, there were on average 316 ± 36 farm fatalities and $127\,000 \pm 16\,000$ non-fatal accidents annually between 2012-2021. To contextualize these figures, there were 4.1 fatalities per 100 000 workers in farming, compared to the all-sectors incidence rate of 1.9 fatalities per 100 000 workers. The corresponding incidence rates for non-fatal accidents were 1 653 and 1 633 accidents per 100 000 workers, respectively. Considering the known occupational risks in farming, such as heavy machinery usage, animal handling, exposure to chemicals, physically demanding tasks, and working in isolated environments, both fatal and non-fatal incidence rates are expected to be higher than the average of all sectors^{1,2,3}. However, this is not the case for non-fatal accidents, suggesting underreporting is a likely issue.

Eurostat acknowledges issues with European Statistics on Accidents at Work data and identifies three primary challenges:

- Differences in the inclusion/exclusion of self-employed, family workers, and other non-employee workers among Member States.
- Accuracy issues with reference populations, which serve as denominators for calculating accident rates.
- Under-reporting of non-fatal accidents in many Member States.

The high proportion of self-employed and family workers in farming mean that these challenges are particularly relevant, and likely to disproportionately affect the production of occupational health and safety accident data. As a consequence, if data users accept the counts of farm accidents and incidence rates at face value, they face a high risk of underestimating the real situation.

Understanding the actual incidence of occupational accidents in agriculture is imperative for several reasons. Firstly, the declining agricultural population over the past decade, largely due to socioeconomic shifts, may also reflect the hazards at work and individuals being forced out of the sector due to injuries. This trend threatens the EU's food security and emphasizes the need for increased resources for prevention. Secondly, underestimation of farm accidents hampers the development of targeted safety measures and interventions crucial for mitigating risks.

In essence, what remains unreported remains unaddressed. To improve working conditions in farming, the quality of life of farmers and farm workers and the social sustainability of European

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² <https://doi.org/10.1080/1059924X.2020.1845268>

³ <https://doi.org/10.13031/2013.15674>

agriculture, a more comprehensive understanding of farm accidents is required if effective policies and strategies are to be developed. This requires improved data collection methodologies and the collection of additional occupational health and safety variables/indicators.

2.2 Objectives

In support of policy stakeholders and policy makers at national and EU levels, the SafeHabitus project was tasked with improving the understanding of the occupational health and safety challenges of farms and developing policy options that enhance working conditions and the attractiveness of farming. To contribute to these aims, the following objectives were developed:

1. Extrapolate from farm injury and fatality data collated by Eurostat and national agencies to estimate the true number of farm injuries and fatalities in EU Member States.
2. Develop a better understanding of national occupational health and safety data systems in selected member states.
3. Demonstrate the use of high quality farm health and safety data to national and EU farm health and safety policy makers and stakeholders.

Objective 1 is pursued by undertaking a desk study that extrapolates from available data to overcome issues of underreporting by estimating injury and fatality rates among countries with similar farm structures and systems. These rates are applied to estimate the true level of farm injuries and deaths across the EU. The results of this research are presented in Section 3.

Objective 2 is pursued by undertaking case studies in each of the 11 SafeHabitus Community of Practice (COP) countries to identify national OSH data collection and reporting systems that cover injuries and illnesses in farming. The results of this research are presented in Section 4.

Objective 3 is achieved by undertaking two case studies to document the utility and impact of high-quality data on policymaking, research, education, and awareness. The two cases are: Finland, where data are collated from claims made against the social insurance system for farmers, and Ireland, where data are collated from occupational fatality incident reports collected by the Health and Safety Authority of Ireland. The results of this research are presented in Sections 5 and 6.

3. Estimating the number of farm accidents and fatalities in the EU

3.1. Data collection approach

A three-stage approach was used to estimate the number of farm fatalities and accidents in the EU. Firstly, Member States with similar types of farms and farming practices were grouped together through cluster analysis. Secondly, higher-quality accident data reported for one or more countries within each group were identified. Thirdly, the occurrence of accidents in the groups was extrapolated based on available data.

For grouping the Member States, data publicly accessible in Eurostat was extracted in February 2023. The data originates from the 2020 Farm Census and 2016 Farm Structure Survey considering data availability during the time of extraction. The full list of data sources, and variables is available in Annex 1. In short, the data extracted cover: 1) the relative importance of agriculture in each member state, indicated by the portion of utilised agricultural area in the total area, the portion of the farm labour force in the population, and the average workload in full-time equivalent of the farm labour force; 2) the division of utilised agricultural area and worktime by farm specialisation, farm size, farm ownership, and characteristic of labour force, and 3) how much training the farm managers have received. All variables were expressed on relative scale, either as ratios or percentages. Statistical software R version 4.2.2, along with the NbClust package for hierarchical cluster analysis and the ade4 package for principal component analysis, was used.

In order to identify member states with higher quality accident data within each group, all three main issues with data were considered: underreporting, coverage of self-employed and family workers, and the accuracy of the reference population. Underreporting, expected to be reflected by incidence rates, served as a basis for comparing member states by the incidence rates of fatal and non-fatal accidents. The use of 5 and 10-year incidence rates was explored; however, 10-year (years 2012 to 2021) incidence rates were chosen to yield non-zero rates even for the very small member states. The 10-year incidence rates (IR_{10}) for each member state were calculated as follows:

$$IR_{10} = \frac{\sum_{2012}^{2021} n_{acc}(i)}{100,000 \times \sum_{2012}^{2021} N_{ref}(i)}$$

where n_{acc} represents the number of non-fatal accidents in the i -th year, and N_{ref} is the number of workers in the reference population in the i -th year. For non-fatal accidents, the number of accidents was obtained from the Eurostat dataset hsw_n2_01, and for fatal accidents from the Eurostat dataset hsw_n2_02. In both cases, the reference population for each year was back-calculated from the number of non-fatal accidents and incidence rates of NACE Rev. 2 class A01 in Eurostat dataset hsw_n2_01 using the following equation:

$$N_{ref} = 100,000 \times \frac{n_{acc}}{IR}$$

Information regarding the coverage of self-employed and family workers in accident data collection was obtained from the European Statistics on Accidents at Work national reference metadata section 3.6.1. For selected member states, this information was cross-checked through inquiries to the member states. Subsequently, the coverage of self-employed and family workers in ESAW and the back-calculated reference population were compared to the agricultural labour force population identified in the Farm Structure Survey (Eurostat dataset ef_if_main) to assess the accuracy of member states' incidence rates. Since the Farm Structure Survey is conducted every three or four years, comparisons can be made for the years 2013, 2016, and 2020. The year 2020 conducted as Agricultural Census and being the most recent year with available data, was chosen for this comparison. To ensure comparability among member states, workers from

holdings that fell below the physical thresholds outlined in Annex II of Regulation (EU) 2018/1091 were excluded. As a result, the total farm labour force used in the estimation amounted to 13.2 million workers.

Member states meeting two criteria were deemed to have higher quality accident data: 1) an accident data collection system covering self-employed and family workers, and 2) IR10 values close to or above the EU27 average. Within three out of five groups, one or more member states were identified that satisfied these criteria. For these member states, the number of accidents remained unchanged during the calculation of the estimated number of accidents. For the remaining member states, the estimated number of accidents was based on the highest IR10 value in the group, unless the selected IR₁₀ was calculated using the EU Labour Force Survey, in which case it was recalculated using the Farm Structure Survey 2020 population. A different estimation approach was used for the two remaining groups. One group comprised member states where the majority of the farm labour force consisted of non-family workers, and ESAW data collection did not cover family workers and only partially covered self-employed workers. In this scenario, the member state's IR10 value was used to extrapolate the number of accidents corresponding to the Farm Structure Survey 2020 population. For the remaining group, an IR value calculated using Polish national data instead of Eurostat data was used. This was because the Polish Agricultural Social Insurance Fund collects accident data of self-employed and family workers, but this data was not reported to Eurostat. Further discussion on this issue can be found in section 4 of the report.

3.2. Estimation of farm fatalities and accidents

The hierarchical cluster analysis revealed five distinctive groups, as illustrated in figure 1. When examining the spatial distribution of these groups on a map (figure 2), it becomes evident that geographical, cultural, and historical factors likely influence the results. The agricultural practices of a country are significantly influenced by its geographic location, impacting crop choices and farming techniques. Additionally, cultural and historical influences likely play a crucial role in determining female participation in agriculture and the ownership structure of agricultural land, whether it is held by legal entities or individuals.

Figure 1. Result of hierarchical cluster analysis of EU member states based on their agricultural land and worktime use.

Figure 2. Map illustrating the geographical proximity of the groups yielded in the hierarchical cluster analysis.

The principal component analysis partially explained the differences among the five groups. Group 1 consists of member states located on the Mediterranean Sea, characterized by a higher share of utilized agricultural area and annual work units dedicated to thematic crops such as olives, vineyards, and fruits. Additionally, this group exhibits a higher share of non-regular workforce and farm managers with basic training in agriculture. Groups 2 and 3 comprise member states from northern and central Europe, distinguished by a higher share of utilized agricultural area allocated to permanent grassland and a greater portion of annual work units dedicated to animal production. These groups also feature a higher annual work units to workers ratio. Groups 4 and 5 encompass member states from Eastern Europe, each with distinct characteristics. Group 4 is marked by a higher share of annual work units in holdings owned by legal persons and a greater proportion of annual work units performed by non-family workforce. In contrast, the defining traits of group 5 include a higher share of the population engaged in agriculture, a greater proportion of annual work units performed by females, and a higher share of holdings with an area less than 5 hectares.

The member states were compared based on their 10-year incidence rates (IR10) of fatal and non-fatal accidents. Figure 3 illustrates this comparison using a scatterplot, with the y-axis representing the member states' incidence rate of fatal accidents and the x-axis representing the incidence rate of non-fatal accidents. A dashed line divides the figure into four quadrants, displaying the EU27 weighted average values of fatal and non-fatal incidence rates. Member states in the lower left quadrant report below-average fatal and non-fatal incidence rates, while those in the upper right quadrant report above-average rates. The figure 3 also suggests that the grouping of member states based on farm types and practices may explain some of the variation in non-fatal accident incidence rates. However, similar non-fatal incidence rates among certain groups may be attributed to underlying cultural and historical factors influencing reporting systems and reporting culture. Therefore, the same data was further analysed by comparing member states with insurance systems for accidents at work and those with universal social security systems (figure 4). Member states with insurance systems for accidents at work tend to have higher incidence rates than member states with universal social security.

Both figures reveal significant variability in both fatal and non-fatal incidence rates among member states. For instance, while the EU27 weighted average 10-year incidence rate for fatal accidents was 4.1 fatalities per 100 000 workers, the lowest incidence rate in a member state was 0.2, and

the highest was 28.9, representing a difference of 183 times. Similarly, for non-fatal accidents, the EU27 weighted average 10-year incidence rate was 1 653, with a minimum of 8 and maximum of 4 722 non-fatal accidents per 100 000 workers observed in a member state, resulting in a difference of 569 times. Such disparities appear unrealistic and are likely due to underreporting and/or the use of inappropriate reference populations in incidence rate calculations. Therefore, additional attention was focused on two key areas: 1) verifying that the statistical population of ESAW includes key worker categories such as self-employed and family workers in accident data collection systems, and 2) verifying that the reference population used to calculate incidence rates corresponds to the size of the farm labour force covered by the accident data collection.

Figure 3. Comparison of incidence rates in Member States by 10-year incidence rates (2012-2021), the colours represent groups of similar types of farms and farming practices, dashed line indicates EU weighted average (Sources: Eurostat hsw_n2_01 & hsw_n2_02).

Figure 4. Comparison of incidence rates in Member States with insurance-based accident notification systems and universal social security system-based systems by 10-year incidence rates (2012-2021), dashed line indicates EU weighted average (Sources: Eurostat hsw_n2_01 & hsw_n2_02).

Table 1 illustrates the coverage of worker categories by member states' accident data collection systems. Given that the majority of the farm labour force comprises family members, the inclusion of self-employed and family workers is crucial to ensure high-quality farm accident data. According to the ESAW national reference metadata, 10 member states have accident data collection systems that fully cover self-employed and family workers, while 9 member states lack systems allowing the collection of accident data from these categories. The remaining 8 states have systems that offer partial coverage of key farm worker categories. In the following seven member states Austria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, Portugal, and Spain, accident insurance systems enable data collection from self-employed and family workers. However, three member states with universal social security systems (Croatia, Ireland, and Sweden) also claim to have accident data collection systems capable of gathering data from self-employed and family workers. A unique situation was uncovered in Poland, where employee accident data is collected by the Polish Social Insurance Institution, while self-employed farmers' accident data is collected by the Polish Agricultural Social Insurance Fund. However, only data from the Polish Social Insurance Institution is reported to Eurostat, as indicated by the shading of these worker categories in table 1. As the proportion of self-employed and family workers varies among member states, the potential effect of excluding these populations on the accuracy of incidence rates was analysed by combining ESAW coverage data with labour force data from the Farm Structure Survey.

Figure 5 displays stacked bar charts illustrating the proportions of non-family workers, self-employed individuals, and family workers in member states' farm labour force in 2020. The colours of the bars, which represent ESAW coverage, provide some insight into the extent to which each member state's farm labour force is covered by accident data collection systems. To assess the potential accuracy of reported incidence rates, a back-calculated reference population value was converted to a percentage of the total farm labour force and depicted with a circle on Figure 5. Ideally, the location of the reference population indicator on the chart should align with the accident data collection coverage. For example, if ESAW coverage includes all worker categories, the reference population should represent the entire farm labour force population, with the circle on Figure 5 positioned at the 100% mark. However, this alignment is not observed for any of the 10 member states where accident data collection systems fully cover self-employed and family workers. This discrepancy is likely due to the use of the EU Labour Force Survey for

reference population. Firstly, the EU Labour Force Survey describes only the domestic population, and secondly, farming is often conducted as a part-time occupation, leading self-employed and family workers to potentially not identify as farm labour in the survey. An alternative to the Labour Force Survey is the use of administrative data sources; however, their effectiveness varies. Figure 5 indicates that in 2020, the administrative data sources of Bulgaria and Romania correspond well to accident data collection. Meanwhile, the 2020 reference population of Germany, at 2 803 300 workers, is 433% higher than the regular farm labour force reported in the Farm Structure Survey, which documented 648 080 workers.

Table 1. Statistical Population ESAW, coverage by professional status (Source: ESAW reference metadata)

Country code	Professional status									
	1	1.1	1.2	2	3	3.1	3.2	3.3	4	5
AT	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
BE	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green
BG	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green
CY	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
CZ	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red
DE	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red
DK	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow
EE	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
EL	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green
ES	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
FI	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red
FR	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red
HR	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
HU	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
IE	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
IT	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	n/a
LT	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
LU	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
LV	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
MT	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
NL	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
PL	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green
PT	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
RO	Yellow	Red	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green
SE	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
SI	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green
SK	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow

ESAW Coverage: ■ - fully covered, ■ - partially covered, ■ - not covered. **Professional status:**
 1. Self employed, 1.1 Self employed with employees, 1.2 Self employed without employees, 2. Family worker, 3. Employee, 3.1 Part time workers, 3.2 Casual workers, 3.3 Trainees/Apprentices, 4. Students, 5. Others.

Colours refer to ESAS coverage: ■ - fully covered, ■ - partially covered, ■ - not covered.

Figure 5. Portion of farm labour force covered by ESAS data collection and relative value of reference population, see legend above the figure (Sources: Eurostat ef_if_main & hsw_n2_01).

All information above was taken into consideration when selecting member states with higher-quality accident data. To qualify as a member state with higher-quality farm accident data, the accident data collection system needed to cover self-employed and family workers, and the 10-year incidence rate needed to be close to or above the EU27 average. Table 2 illustrates how member states met these criteria. Out of 27 member states, 11 have accident data collection systems that include self-employed and family workers, but only 10 member states report this data to Eurostat, as accident data collected by the Polish Agricultural Social Insurance Fund remains unreported. Among the 11 member states meeting the accident data collection criterion, 6 reported fatal and non-fatal incidence rates close to or above the EU27 average. Additionally, two member states reported below EU27 average non-fatal incidence rates and above-average fatal incidence rates.

Table 2. Fulfilment of higher-quality accident data criteria by member states; I – existence of an accident data collection system that cover self-employed and family workers; II - IR10 values close to or above the EU27 average.

Criterion	Member state										
	AT	DE	ES	FI	HR	IE	IT	LU	PL	PT	SE
I	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+	+
II	+	+	+	+	-	+/-	+	+	-	-	+/-

Examining the fulfilment of higher-quality accident data (Table 2) among groups of member states with similar types of farms and farming practices (Figure 1), it becomes apparent that multiple member states in groups 1 to 3 meet the criteria for higher-quality accident data. However, in the case of group 4, no member states meet these criteria, and for group 5, two member states partially meet the criteria for higher-quality accident data.

Considering that member states with different types of farms and farming practices may exhibit varying incidence rates, it is plausible that some groups identified in the hierarchical cluster analysis could consist entirely of member states reporting incidence rates below the EU27 average. Therefore, a closer examination of accident data from Croatia and Poland was undertaken. A comparison between Eurostat data and Polish national data⁴ revealed that only data from the Polish Social Insurance Institution is reported to Eurostat, with a perfect match observed for fatal accidents and an average difference of 2% noted for non-fatal accidents. However, the vast majority of Polish farm fatalities and non-fatal accidents were not reported to Eurostat. This discrepancy is highly problematic, as 53 fatalities were reported to Eurostat between 2012 and 2021, however the 679 fatalities collected by the Polish Agricultural Social Insurance Fund in the same period remained unreported. Furthermore, the reference population used by Eurostat for incidence rate calculations is more suitable for the entire Polish farm labour force population than for the small fraction covered by the Polish Social Insurance Institution. This partly explains why Poland shows one of the lowest incidence rates among member states in Figures 3 and 4. If both sources were included in the incidence rate calculation, the incidence rates for fatal and non-fatal accidents would be respectively 7 and 10 times higher than currently reported. According to Polish national data, an average of 73 fatal accidents and 13 648 non-fatal accidents occurred annually between 2012 and 2021. Utilizing Poland's 2020 Farm Structure Survey, which reported a farm labour population of 2 174 440 workers, incidence rates were calculated at 3.4 for fatal accidents and 627.7 for non-fatal accidents per 100 000 workers. Applying these incidence rates to the total farm labour population of Group 4, as reported in the 2020 Farm Structure Survey, which amounted to 5 081 800 workers, the estimated number of fatal accidents is 171, and the estimated number of non-fatal accidents is 31 896.

Group 4, composed of Estonia, Czechia, and Slovakia, did not have any member states with an accident data collection system covering self-employed and family workers. Consequently, it was decided that incidence rates from Eurostat would be utilized to calculate the number of fatal and

⁴ <https://stat.gov.pl/en/topics/labour-market/working-conditions-accidents-at-work/accidents-at-work-in-2021,3,15.html>

non-fatal accidents for the entire farm labour force. Given that the majority of the farm labour force in this group comprises employees, the estimation is reasonably accurate, even though self-employed and family workers might have different incidence rates than employees. According to Eurostat, an average of $2\,631 \pm 690$ non-fatal and 11 ± 4 fatal accidents occurred annually within Group 4 between 2012 and 2021. Using each member state's 10-year incidence rate within Group 4 and applying it to the 2020 Farm Structure Survey's farm labour population yields an estimated 14 fatal and 3 479 non-fatal accidents.

Group 3, comprising Austria, Ireland, Luxembourg, and Slovenia, exhibited a mixture of higher-quality accident data among its member states. Two member states had higher-quality non-fatal accident data, while three member states had higher-quality fatal accident data. The number of fatal and non-fatal accidents reported by member states with higher-quality accident data remained unchanged during the estimation process. For the rest the number of non-fatal accidents were calculated by using Austrian non-fatal accident incidence rate and Irish fatal incidence rate. Before applying these rates to other member states, adjustments were made to accommodate the full farm labour force population. The adjusted Austrian non-fatal accident incidence rate and Irish fatal incidence rate were calculated by using the average number of accidents in the last decade as the numerator and the 2020 Farm Structure Survey's farm labour force population as the denominator. According to Eurostat, an average of $4\,715 \pm 863$ non-fatal and 60 ± 12 fatal accidents occurred annually within Group 3 between 2012 and 2021. The estimated number of non-fatal accidents increased to 9 103, and the number of fatal accidents increased to 69.

In Group 2, Finland and Germany were identified as member states with higher-quality accident data, and the number of fatal and non-fatal accidents were not altered during the estimation process. For the remaining member states, the Finnish adjusted incidence rates were applied. According to Eurostat, an average of $66\,131 \pm 12\,363$ non-fatal and 100 ± 17 fatal accidents occurred annually within Group 2 between 2012 and 2021. The estimated number of non-fatal accidents in this group is 90 421 and fatal accidents is 126.

In Group 1, Italy, Portugal, and Spain were identified as member states with higher-quality accident data, and the number of fatal and non-fatal accidents were not altered during the estimation process. For the remaining member states, the Italian adjusted incidence rates were applied. According to Eurostat, an average of $51\,425 \pm 3\,741$ non-fatal and 109 ± 13 fatal accidents occurred annually within Group 2 between 2012 and 2021. The estimated number of non-fatal accidents in this group is 71 295 and fatal accidents is 164.

Altogether, an average of 315 ± 36 fatal and $126\,817 \pm 16\,390$ non-fatal accidents were reported to Eurostat annually between 2012 and 2021. The estimated number of fatal accidents is 545, and the estimated number of non-fatal accidents is 206 194. Figures 6 and 7 illustrate the difference between reported and estimated accidents by groups of member states with similar types of farms and farming practices. One factor determining the total accidents in each group is the farm labour force population. However, neither the number of member states nor the size of the farm labour force is consistent across the groups. According to the 2020, Farm Structure Survey, only groups 1 and 5 are of comparable size, with 5 177 470 people in group 1 and 5 081 800 people in group 5. The remaining groups (2, 3, and 4) are smaller and of varying sizes, with 1 995 250 people in group 2 708 760 people in group 3, and 219 730 people in group 4.

Figure 6. Reported and estimated annual farm fatalities, with error bars representing the standard deviation for the reported average. Refer to figure 2 for member states in the groups.

Several factors influence the difference between reported and estimated accidents:

- i. The number of member states with higher-quality accident data in each group.
- ii. The size of these countries compared to the rest of the member states in the group.
- iii. The incidence rate values of member states with higher-quality accident data compared to the rest of the member states in the group.
- iv. The worker categories covered by the accident data collection systems and relative proportion of the worker categories covered by the accident data collection systems.

Figure 7. Reported and estimated annual farm accidents, with error bars representing the standard deviation for the reported average. Refer to figure 2 for the member states included in the groups.

In the extreme case of group 5, the estimation was based on higher-quality Polish national data, resulting in alterations to the number of accidents for every member state in the group during the estimation process. Additionally, as evident from Figure 5, member states in group 5 tend to collect accident data only about employees, leading to a difference of 4.8 times in reported and estimated fatal accidents and 16.7 times in the case of non-fatal accidents. Conversely, in group 3, three out of four member states had higher-quality fatal accident data, resulting in only a 1.2 times difference between reported and estimated fatal accidents.

Through the process of estimating farm fatalities and accidents, several conclusions emerge, shedding light on data quality issues and pointing toward potential solutions:

1. Despite family labour being the primary workforce in EU agriculture, only 11 member states (as shown in Table 1) have accident data collection systems capable of capturing data from both self-employed and family workers. Coverage of these worker categories is crucial, given potential differences in their accident incidence rates compared to employees. Currently, member states with such systems predominantly employ insurance-based accident notification systems.
2. Member states utilizing insurance-based accident notification systems tend to exhibit higher incidence rates of non-fatal accidents (as depicted in Figure 4).
3. The accuracy of incidence rates depends on acquiring precise accident data and utilizing a reference population aligned with the worker categories included in accident data collection. Given that the reference population used in incidence rate calculations appears misaligned with the worker categories covered by ESAW data collection (as illustrated in Figure 5), a revision of reference population data sources is warranted.

4. Findings: Who gets counted in occupational health and safety statistics? A comparison of 11 EU member states

While Table 1 already describes which worker categories are covered by the accident data collection systems of member states, discussions with stakeholders indicated the need for narrower categorization of worker categories to enhance the understanding of data collection and reporting of farm accidents. Therefore, a survey was conducted among the 11 SafeHabitus national Community of Practice countries (Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Spain). The survey comprised four stages: 1) introduction and description of the data collection system, 2) description of the reference population, 3) collection and reporting of non-fatal accidents data, and 4) collection and reporting of fatal accidents data.

In the **first stage**, the Communities of Practice were required to describe the type of member states' accident reporting procedures, review recent accident data, and compare it to national sources. The majority of the 11 EU member states had systems based on the legal obligation of the employers to notify the accidents to the relevant national authorities, which means that accident data collection and temporary working incapacity benefits are the responsibility of different organizations. Three member states (France, Finland, and Germany) have statutory insurance for the farmers, in which case both the accident data collection and temporary working incapacity benefits are handled by the same organization. Three member states (Lithuania, Poland, and Spain) claim to have mixed systems, meaning employees of legal person-owned farms and self-employed or family workers of natural person-owned farms are subject to different rules for accident data collection and temporary working incapacity benefits. The comparison of nationally and Eurostat-reported accident data was not possible in the case of two member states, as Estonia and Lithuania do not nationally publish accident data on NACE Rev.2 two-digit level. For the rest, the values were either a perfect match or had small differences in most cases, likely due to differences in reporting criteria of non-fatal accidents. Eurostat reports non-fatal accidents with >3 days of work incapacity, while some member states' national reporting also includes non-fatal accidents with 1 to 3 days of work incapacity. The second source of differences is the inclusion of commuting accidents in the national reporting of some member states. While the number of accidents was comparable between Eurostat and member states' reported data, some Communities of Practice expressed doubts whether Eurostat and member states use the same reference populations to calculate incidence rates.

In the **second stage of the survey**, Communities of Practice were asked to provide information about the reference population, including who and how individuals are counted in the reference population and which national data sources are available. According to the ESAW reference metadata section 18.1, the reference populations are either provided by the countries (at NACE Rev.2. two-digits level) or sourced from the EU Labour Force Survey when countries are unable to provide their own reference populations. Figure 8 depicts the comparison of the reference population and the EU Labour Force Survey (LFS). Yearly reference population values are normalized to yearly LFS population values, meaning a 100% value indicates that the member state's reference population value for a year is equal to the LFS population value of that year. Significant differences from 100% mean that the LFS population was likely not used as the reference population. In the majority of cases, the normalised reference population is at or below the LFS population value. One clear exception is Germany, whose reference population is 5 to 6 times greater than the population identified in the LFS. Through the survey, it was clarified that the German reference population is calculated by the internally developed method of the Social Insurance for Agriculture, Forestry, and Horticulture. The calculation takes into account the self-employed and family workers, full-time non-family workers, and also worker categories that are not included in the LFS population, such as non-regular domestic and foreign workers (seasonal workers). It is worth exploring if and to what extent the method used to calculate the German

reference population can be applied to other member states

Figure 8. Inconsistencies in the use of reference populations demonstrated by the comparison of ESAW reference populations normalised to EU Labour Force Survey (LFS) population of 15-year-olds and older. Each dot represents a single year, with box and whisker plots added for visual grouping. Rare deviations are labelled with the year of occurrence, and off-scale values are labelled with the corresponding percentage value.

In the case of Estonia, Finland, Ireland, Slovakia, and Spain, the ESAW reference population closely aligns with the LFS population. Some deviations are likely due to differences in the age classes used. For the calculations in Figure 8, the age class of '15 years or over' was utilized. However, using an age class that represents only the working-age population, such as the age class 'from 15 to 64 years' old, would result in a higher value of normalized reference population. Through the survey, it was noted that in Estonia, for some years, the entire LFS population was used as a reference population, while for other years, only the portion of the LFS population corresponding to employees with contracts was utilized. The latter approach is considered more appropriate for the Estonian reference population, as it aligns with the accident data collection system. The remaining five member states (France, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovenia) have reference populations that significantly deviate from the LFS population, as either their data collection or reporting to Eurostat excludes part of the farming population. Some issues with data were identified during the survey. In the case of Lithuania, it was revealed that instead of NACE Rev.2 two-digits level data (i.e., 'Crop and animal production, hunting, and related service activities'), one-digit level data (i.e., 'Agriculture, forestry, and fishing') is sent to Eurostat, where the data is transformed to NACE Rev.2 two-digits level reference population value. In the case of Romania, the reference population needs to represent only employees to align with worker groups covered by data collection. Therefore, the reference population value for the year 2019 is not correct and significantly lowers the incidence rate. In the case of Slovenia, the reference population should be the number of workers insured by the Health Insurance Institute of Slovenia. The survey answer indicated that, at least for the years 2019 and 2020, the ESAW reference population does not match the reference population provided by the member states. In the case of Poland, the ESAW reference population does not match the accident data reported, as employee and self-employed farmers' accident data is collected by different institutions, and only employee accident data is reported to Eurostat. The Polish ESAW reference population also shows unwarranted variations, fluctuating between 0.2 to 1.8 million workers, while calculations based on the data in annual editions of 'Accidents at work' by Statistics Poland suggest that a more appropriate value would be around 60,000 workers. This results in unjust representation of Polish fatal and non-fatal accident data in Eurostat.

In the **third stage of the survey**, Communities of Practice were asked to provide information about non-fatal accidents, including what information is available nationally in addition to what is

reported to Eurostat. As mentioned in the first stage of the survey, one of the differences between what is reported to Eurostat and what is reported nationally is the inclusion of accidents that resulted in temporary work incapacity of less than three days or, in some cases, accidents without lost time, i.e., minor work accidents. In some member states (Lithuania, Poland, Spain), an additional class of serious accidents exists, defined as accidents resulting in serious bodily harm, such as loss of sight, hearing, speech, ability to procreate, or other bodily harm or health-related problems that disrupt primary bodily functions or result in an incurable and life-threatening disease, permanent mental illness, permanent total or significant incapacity for work in the occupation, or permanent significant disfigurement or distortion of the body. Other notable differences include the national reporting of 'dangerous occurrences' by Ireland and the collection of data related to accidents that happen to people visiting the site with the employer's permission.

One of the inquiries in stage three of the survey was to detail whether various categories of people are included in the data reported to Eurostat and what potential reasons exist for underreporting. The following 10 categories were used:

1. Self-employed Farmer without employees
2. Self-employed Farmer with employees
3. Farmer's family salaried by farm
4. Farmer's family not salaried by farm
5. Regular workers (full time or part time)
6. Non-regular domestic workers (seasonal workers)
7. Non-regular foreign workers (seasonal workers)
8. Substitute or relief workers (incident happens on farm)
9. Contractors (incident happens on farm)
10. Bystanders (incident happens on farm)

There are no differences in the reporting of accidents related to regular workers; once the workers are insured or have employment contracts, they are covered by the data collection system. In the case of non-regular workers, the origin of the workers (domestic, foreign) makes no difference; in most cases, the same rules for inclusion (e.g., insurance, employment contract) apply. However, in the case of Slovenia and Romania, accidents with non-regular workers are not reported to Eurostat. In the case of services like substitute workers and contractors, reporting depends on whether these workers are hired as workers (the same rules apply as in the case of non-regular workers) or work for service providers (reporting depends on the NACE of the service provider). Accidents with bystanders are not reported to Eurostat, as they do not qualify as occupational accidents.

In the case of self-employed farmers, the situation is more complex. In Estonia, accidents with self-employed workers are excluded from occupational health statistics. In Poland, self-employed farmers' accidents are collected and reported nationally but not to Eurostat. Lithuania, Romania, and Slovakia have different rules for self-employed farmers with and without employees. In Romania, all accidents with self-employed farmers are collected; however, only those accidents that happen with self-employed farmers without employees are reported to Eurostat. In Lithuania and Slovakia, it is the opposite. In the case of the remaining six member states, accidents with self-employed farmers are both collected and reported to Eurostat, provided that the farmers have either accident or health insurance.

Regarding family members, the same rules as for regular workers apply to family members salaried by the farm, and the same rules as for self-employed farmers apply to family members who are not salaried by the farm. Except in Lithuania, where all family workers are excluded from occupational accident data collection.

Underreporting of non-fatal accidents on farms arises due to various reasons. In cases where universal healthcare covers medical expenses, there's often no incentive to report accidents, particularly for minor accidents, as they might not require extensive medical attention. The uniformity of reporting systems across all employers compounds the issue, as there's a general lack of motivation to adhere to mandatory reporting requirements. Moreover, farmers are reluctant to draw the attention of labour inspectors to their farms, leading to widespread non-reporting of

accidents, despite legal obligations. Additionally, fear of losing one's job deters reporting by the workers, and a portion of farm workers are thought to be employed in the informal economy.

In the **fourth stage of the survey**, Communities of Practice were asked to provide information about fatal accidents, mirroring the process followed in the third stage for non-fatal accidents. The results from the third and fourth stages were nearly identical, as the data collection systems for fatal and non-fatal accidents generally do not differ. However, there were notable exceptions, such as in Ireland, where the investigative approach is believed to result in nearly 100% accident collection and reporting. Additionally, in Poland, a deviation from ESAW's definition of fatal accidents was observed. In Poland, a fatal accident at work is defined as an accident during which the injured person dies either at the accident site or within 6 months from the date of the accident.

The following conclusions emerge from the four-stage survey:

- Reference populations used to calculate incidence rates show unwarranted variations, some likely caused by the use of inappropriate reference populations. As these variations become evident when examined over time or in comparison, such as in Figure 8, regular checks on reference population data are warranted. These checks ensure that comparisons of member states or fields of the economy by incidence rates do not lead to false interpretations of the situation.
- Accurate incidence rates require reference populations that align with the population covered by accident data collection system. Notably, the EU Labour Force Survey lacks inclusion of foreign workers, and the part time workers are likely excluded as well. Therefore, exploring the potential of applying the method used to calculate the German reference population among other member states should be considered.
- In the survey the disincentive to report non-fatal accident data were mainly indicated by those member states where accident data collection and temporary work incapacity benefits are not handled by the same organisations. This means that member states with accident insurance tend to have higher-quality accident data.

Discussion

Johnson et al.⁵ reports the incidence rate of non-fatal agricultural injuries in Central United states to be 7 000 per 100 000 person-years and cites studies reporting incidence rates in agriculture ranging from 2 900 to 16 600 per 100 000 workers. The corresponding value reported by Eurostat, 1 653 non-fatal accidents per 100 000 workers, is significantly lower. On the one hand the incidence rate of EU and studies about US refer to different quantities, as the USA rate likely refers to all accidents while EU rate refers to accidents resulting in >3 days of work incapacity. On the other hand, the 1 653 accidents per 100 000 workers is the average meaning that a significant proportion of member state report even lower rates. The high variation in the incidence rates of the members states has raised concerns in the scientific community. Merisalu et al.⁶ list potential causes for this variation: a) farm structure, b) use of reference populations, c) under-reporting, and d) different inclusion/exclusion criteria. The SafeHabitus set out to focus on accounting the differences in farm structure, however, all other factors had to be considered in the process.

The differences in farm structure known to affect incidence rates include farm specialisation in crop or animal production^{7,8}, terrain and crops⁹, gender¹⁰, and education¹¹ of the worker. All these factors were taken into account when grouping member states with similar types of farms and

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1080/1059924X.2020.1845268>

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.15159/AR.19.190>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1080/1059924X.2023.2293840>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.13031/jash.22.11244>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12071694>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2021.105422>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.1080/1059924X.2016.1179611>

farming practices together. Previous studies on EU agriculture have commonly employed cluster analysis at the level of European NUTS2 regions^{12,13}. However, despite this, there is a recurring pattern of dividing EU agriculture into distinct geographical regions: northern-central, southern, and eastern Europe. In our study, grouping was conducted at the member state level due to the unavailability of accident data at the NUTS 2 regional level. Surprisingly, a study focusing on the production potential of dairy farms¹⁴ also opted for grouping at the member state level, closely mirroring our results by having two groups in Eastern Europe and grouping together Estonia, Czechia, and Slovakia. In our study, the five groups containing member states with geographical, cultural, and historical links posed their own challenges. On the one hand, in a group of culturally and historically similar member states, a shared reporting culture may be one of the factors influencing incidence rates. On the other hand, if grouping is based on factors that affect incidence rates, this may impact the incidence rates at the group level. For example, Group Five, containing many Eastern European member states, showed below EU27 average incidence rates. However, the group is characterized by a higher share of women workers and a lower share of animal production, and both factors are associated with lower odds of accidents^{15,16,17}.

The estimation study indicates significant underreporting, and the approach used for estimation allows for repeating the procedure once the next Farm Structure Survey data becomes available. However, the underlying issue of missing data becomes apparent when examining the estimated numbers of fatal and non-fatal accidents. The estimated number of 545 fatalities exceeds the average reported number of 315 fatalities by 1.7 times, while the estimated number of 206 000 non-fatal accidents surpasses the average reported number of 127 000 non-fatal accidents by 1.6 times. While the number of accidents may be estimated, other variables describing the accident are lost. Meanwhile, it's the detailed information about the accidents that allows the comprehensive identification of risk factors, development of effective prevention programs, and assessment of the effectiveness of different technologies and practices in preventing injuries¹⁸. In line with this, Meredith et al.¹⁹ argue that multiple incidence rates (i.e., separate rates for farmers, family workers, and employees) are preferred to an overall incidence rate to adequately communicate the nature of farm safety issues. Achieving this will need an approach that is more tailored to the specifics of farming. While some⁶ propose introducing new surveys, others¹⁸ propose combining injury and Farm Accountancy Data Network data (now called Farm Sustainability Data Network). If new approaches to collect farm accident data are implemented, they should be designed to avoid one of the key issues of European Statistics on Accidents at Work - the separation of accident and reference population data collection. In that regard, it is worth exploring the introduction of farm injuries variables and indicators within the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FSDN), the EU Farm Structure Survey (FSS) and EU Agricultural Census. In addition to the collection of data on farm characteristics (FSS and Census) and performance (FSDN), these data collection processes also collect information regarding the reference populations, i.e. the labour force.

¹² <https://doi.org/10.17306/J.JARD.2018.01105>

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.17221/154/2021-AGRICECON>

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture10040092>

¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2021.105422>

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.13031/2013.15674>

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.13031/jash.22.11244>

¹⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1080/1059924X.2020.1837704>

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1080/1059924X.2022.2113196>

5. Ireland: Case Study of Fatal Farm Injuries Data

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Introduction

Quantitative and qualitative data are critical to understand the frequency of occupational and workplace incidents on farms, determine the causes of these incidents, and, most importantly, development of preventive measures that support increased knowledge, awareness and adoption of safer farming practices. Ireland represents an interesting case as all fatal incidents that occur on farms or in the course of undertaking farm work are recorded regardless of the age or employment status of the victim. These data are used to inform a variety of approaches that are implemented by a range of stakeholders to inform policy and strategy, increase awareness of the need for the adoption of safe farm practices, guide education and training initiatives including those implemented through the Farm Advisory Service (FAS).

In this case study we provide an overview of the farm fatalities surveillance system including; the policy and governance framework, the collection process, and the variables collected. We then describe the functioning of the surveillance system to showcase how these data are used by a variety of stakeholders ranging from national to local levels.

Farms and the farm labour force in Ireland

In 2020 there were 135 037 farm holdings in Ireland with an average farm size of 36ha²⁰. Most farms are involved in rearing livestock. The vast majority of farms, 99.7%, in Ireland are owned and operated by farm families²¹. Associated with this, most farm work is undertaken by self-employed farm holders with additional labour provided by family members. The average age of a farm holder in Ireland is 57 whilst the largest group of farmers, both male and female, are those 65 years of age and older²².

In line with trends seen across the EU, the number of farms is decreasing whilst farm size is increasing. It has become increasingly difficult to attract people to work on farms due to low incomes, the physically demanding nature of the work and competition from other sectors for workers. This has resulted in the need to attract workers from outside of Ireland to work on farms. Over time, the number of non-family workers has increased on farms in Ireland. This is driven by an increase in the intensity of food production, particularly in horticulture and, in recent years, the dairy sector. There are estimated to be 7 464 workers (employees), of which 77% are foreign nationals (Teagasc, 2022).

Governance of Farm Safety in Ireland

Legislative background and population coverage. The Irish OHS surveillance system governing agriculture is grounded in legislation. Under the Safety, Health, and Welfare at Work Act²³ (SHWWA) (2005), the Health and Safety Authority (HSA) serves as the national statutory body responsible for documenting all work-related fatal and non-fatal incidents across all economic sectors, including 'Agriculture, Forestry, and Fishing'. The Safety, Health, and Welfare at Work Act defines a workplace incident as a fatal or non-fatal injury arising out of or in the course of employment. Under the act, all employers and self-employed persons are required to ensure

²⁰ <https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-coa/censusofagriculture2020-preliminaryresults/farmstructure/>

²¹ <https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-fss/farmstructuresurvey2016/da/fofi/>

²² <https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-coa/censusofagriculture2020detailedresults/agriculturelabourforce/>

²³ <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2005/act/10/enacted/en/pdf>

the health and safety of themselves and others who may be affected by their work activities. This includes conducting risk assessments, implementing necessary safety measures, providing appropriate training, and complying with relevant health and safety regulations and guidelines. The inclusion of self-employed persons, who are legally considered to be their own 'employer', is a relatively novel approach in the EU context, i.e. in several countries these workers are not covered by either occupational health and safety (OSH) regulations and hence, are not considered within the OSH surveillance system.

Figure 9. Age Profile of Fatal Farm Injuries in Ireland (2004 – 2018)

All fatal incidents related to farm work activities, including those involving farmers/farm operators, farm workers, family members, and bystanders, are reported in the national statistics. This comprehensive approach ensures coverage of all vulnerable cohorts and distinguishes it from regulatory systems that only report incidents affecting employees of working age. The significance of this approach is evident in Figure 9. There were 274 fatalities in the period 2004 – 2018. Whilst 48% of the victims of these fatalities were of working age, i.e. between 15 and 64 years of age, 10% were less than 15 or 42% were over 64

years of age. If the HSA only concerned itself with fatalities to those between the ages of 15 and 64, the deaths of 142 people would have been excluded, i.e. these victims would have been made invisible and key lessons would go unlearned.

Investigating Fatalities

The HSA conducts an investigation on notification of a fatal farm injury. This can be reported by either farmers/farm operators, other family members, the police or local coroner. An inspector is tasked to visit the location of the fatality and undertake an investigation to establish the cause(s) of the incident. As part of this process, the inspector records demographic and incident characteristics. These reports are used to produce data that are recorded in a farm fatalities dataset (FFD). The dataset includes variables describing personal characteristics (age in years, gender, type of farm, e.g. dairy, beef, tillage etc., location of farm and location of incident on the farm) and injury characteristics (cause of incident, cause of injury, time of injury (hour, day, month, and season), and a brief, qualitative description (Table 3).

Data Utilisation

These data provide a comprehensive overview of fatal farm injuries and are the basis of the Farm Health and Safety Knowledge Innovation System in Ireland. Figure 10 summarises the structure of the system by classifying key components in terms of Inputs, Activities, Outputs and Outcomes. Inputs describe the legislative and governance framework as described in section 5.3 above. 'Activities' covers a wide range of uses of the data from the production of initial fatality reports which are shared with high-level policy stakeholders including the Minister for Farm Safety, to data analysis and dissemination. Activities can be categorised in terms of core functions associated with the HSA, including data collection, processing, and stakeholder co-ordination. Outputs describe the range of 'products' resulting from the analysis and use of the data whilst Outcomes identifies target impact areas. These latter area involve a range of organisations and stakeholders many of

who are members of the Farm Safety Partnership Advisory Committee (FSPAC)²⁴. The committee is an important element of the Irish approach to reducing farm fatalities (and non-fatal injuries). It is the advisory committee on issues relating to agriculture to the Board of the HSA. The FSPAC was established to involve industry stakeholders in improving occupational safety and health in Agriculture. Whilst it has several objectives, key priorities include:

1. To act as a consultative and advisory forum on the HSA's priorities and work programme for the Agriculture Sector.
2. To develop and agree a national farm safety action plan, coordinate the actions of working groups and representative organisations.
3. To identify, prioritise and progress key actions related to improving safety and health standards in the Agriculture Sector.

One objective that is not explicitly set out in the FSPAC Terms of Reference is the communication and dissemination of key outputs or initiatives that are produced or developed by members of the partnership. This is particularly important in amplification of key safety messages and their subsequent coverage by national, regional and local media, including farming media.

Table 3. Fatal farm injuries variables reported by the HSA

Geographic coverage		Worksites	
National	*	Farm	*
Region	*	Farmyard	*
County	*	Fields	*
Local	*	Farm Buildings	*
Socio-demographic characteristics		Public road	*
Age	*	Other	*
Gender	*	Cause/Trigger	
Nationality	*	Tractor	*
Type of Farm Enterprise	*	Machinery	*
Work arrangements		Livestock	*
Self-employed	*		*
		Drowning / Asphyxiation	*
Employed	*	Falls from Heights	*
Family Worker	*	Falling Objects / Collapse	*
Bystander	*	Forest/Timber related	*
Time		Electrocution	*
Date and Time	*	Other	*

²⁴ Further information can be found here:

https://www.hsa.ie/eng/your_industry/agriculture_forestry/overview/farm_safety_partnership_advisory_committee/

Figure 10. The Farm Health and Safety Knowledge Innovation System in Ireland

Policy and Strategy

A review of farm safety policy and strategies, highlights the extensive use of farm fatality data collected by the HSA, to inform agricultural development policies³¹, national action plans³³ and organisational strategies³². Farm fatality data have been extensively used to highlight the overrepresentation of farm or farming related incidents in national occupational health and safety statistics. This is evident in the national Food Vision 2030²⁵, the Farm Safety Action plan (2021-2024)²⁶ developed by the HSA to foster synergies between policy, regulation, industry, research and education; and the Teagasc Together strategy (2021 – 2024)²⁷ which includes a strategic goal to enhance the safety, health and wellbeing of farmers and farm families. The Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM) has also used the data and associated analyses to identify priority funding for the adoption of safety enhancing equipment or machinery, and the improvement of animal handling facilities. This is funded through the Targeted Agricultural Modernisation Scheme (TAMS)²⁸.

Research

The HSA and a number of other organisations, particularly Teagasc, the Irish Agriculture and Food Development Authority draw on the data contained in the farm fatalities dataset to provide detailed analyses of track injury causations and emerging risks, understand risk taking, identify prevention strategies, and develop and implement targeted prevention strategies.

The HSA produce a range of summary statistical report that assess trends and causes of fatal injuries. These reports provide detailed insights into the 'when', 'where', 'who' and 'how' of farm fatalities. These data have also been used by Teagasc researchers to develop key insights into the multidimensional characteristics of farm fatalities²⁹ and the calculation of fatality rates³⁰ for a range of subgroups within the population at risk of fatal farm injuries, e.g. farm families, children, farm holders (legal owners), family workers, and non-family workers. A full list of published research, including health and

TARGETED AGRICULTURAL MODERNISATION SCHEME 3 (TAMS 3) - Farm Safety Capital Investment Scheme

TAMS is jointly funded by the European Union and the national exchequer. It provides for grant aid of completed and eligible expenditure and shall be paid at the rate of 60% for specified 'farm safety' investments. Eligible investments include certain buildings and facilities, e.g. for animal handling, and equipment, e.g. covers for slurry storage tanks, mobile animal handling equipment, and livestock monitors.

To be eligible for funding all applicants must have completed, within the last five years, the half day Farm Safety Code of Practice training course or have completed the FETAC Level 6 new award system QQ1 Advanced Certificate in Agriculture (Green Cert.).

²⁵ <https://assets.gov.ie/179696/6c6b405e-7c06-4f23-82c0-9edaf7d70a8a.pdf>

²⁶ https://www.hsa.ie/eng/publications_and_forms/publications/agriculture_and_forestry/farm-safety-action-plan-2021-2024.pdf

²⁷ <https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2021/Teagasc-Statement-of-Strategy.pdf>

²⁸ <https://assets.gov.ie/259166/1bddd139-e102-4b07-b6c8-6ad87e165869.pdf>

²⁹ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1059924X.2022.2116138?src=recsys>

³⁰ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1059924X.2022.2113196>

non-fatal articles, is presented in Annex 2. These analyses inform both general awareness raising activities and also targeted 'Risk Based' inspection campaigns (See below).

Awareness raising campaigns and training (from children to older farmers)

A range of public, private and industry representative organisations draw on the farm fatalities data to highlight the challenges that farming presents to safety and health. Through close collaboration, the HSA and Teagasc have developed a range of data-driven tools and training programs aimed at raising awareness and promoting farm safety among various groups. These initiatives support the identification of high-risk or vulnerable populations, e.g. older farmers, children, family members, farm workers, or young farmers. With a primary focus on risk and hazard identification, these training programs and tools are designed to reach the most vulnerable individuals within the farming community^{20,21,30}. Private sector businesses, particularly the farming media, social enterprises (<https://www.agrikids.ie/>) and industry representative organisations. The graphic presented below is part of a joint initiative between two private organisations, the Irish Farmers Association and the Farm Business Development insurance company to highlight the risks associated with slurry gases (Figure 11).

Targeted Campaigns

The FFD is analysed to identify key causes of fatalities, populations that are particularly vulnerable to these risks and the locations and times of the year when they are most likely to occur. Based on these analyses, targeted awareness raising campaigns are undertaken. Each campaign involves national and local media engagement and farm safety audits that are undertaken by HSA occupational safety specialists, i.e. inspectors. In 2024, four 'campaigns' are planned. These are:

- Livestock Safety –2 weeks (22nd Jan to 2nd Feb).
- Tractors/Quads/Machinery –2 weeks (29th April to 10th May).
- Forestry Safety –1 week (22nd July to 26th July).
- Work at Height –2 weeks (2nd Sept to 19th Sept).
- Farmer Health and Wellbeing –1 week (18th Nov to 22nd Nov).

Figure 11. Example of industry organisation's use of farm fatalities data.

Risk assessment tools and preventive measures

The data have played a significant role in the development of the Farm Safety Code of Practice, and the Risk Assessment (RA) tool³⁵, both of which have gained substantial adoption among Irish farmers, reaching almost 70% of them³³ (Table 3). It is a legal requirement to have a safety statement which includes a risk assessment on farms with four or more employees. For farms with three or less people working, they can use the Farm Safety Code of Practice to comply with their legal requirement. The RAD and the FSCP presents a summary major risks and the causes of incidents, supplemented by illustrative content and action tables that supports farmers to identify risks and hazards, as well as in planning safety actions to create a safe working environment. As noted above, the RAD is a mandatory requirement for farmers applying grant aid under the TAMS³⁶.

Figure 12. Health and Safety Authority Farm Safety Code of Practice

Development of preventive measures

Whilst raising awareness and education and training initiatives, e.g. the RAD training provided by Teagasc, are key elements in the strategies that are in place to improve farm safety and reduce the number of fatal and non-fatal injuries, more targeted approaches are necessary. The HSA has developed a range of guidance documents³¹ to support farmers and farm families identify and manage risks including those associated with handling livestock, calving, lambing, managing fatigue, tractors, machinery, working at height etc.

Teagasc has used the data as a means of prioritising the development of education and training initiatives that are delivered through the Teagasc farm advisory service (

Table 4).

Table 4. Overview of farm safety knowledge transfer approaches informed by farm fatalities data.

Focus Area	Focus issues	Overview
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³¹ https://www.hsa.ie/eng/publications_and_forms/publications/agriculture_and_forestry/

Dairy Safety	Reducing falls from tractors and attacks by livestock	Co-design, piloting and evaluation of a knowledge transfer approach involving farmers and farm advisors. The primary focus was on farmers with a dairy enterprise as these are the location of a disproportionate number of fatal injuries.
Work Organisation	Reducing trips and falls; reducing fatigue	Implementation of a practical work planning tool by farm advisors with farmers. The tool focused reducing time pressure on farmers as this was identified as a key factor in incidents leading to a fatality, particularly those associated with 'trips and falls'.
Machinery Safety	Reducing incidents where tractors strike bystanders	Tractors and machinery are leading causes of fatalities on farms. The research co-designed, piloted and evaluated a 'train-the-trainer' approach involving farmers and farm advisors.

Conclusions

Overall, the utilisation of high quality FFI data has been pivotal in the formulation of farm safety strategy, research, awareness raising, guidelines and risk management tools, and safety education and training initiatives in Ireland. Whilst these data are central to the activities of, particularly, the HSA and Teagasc, they are also utilised by a range of other stakeholders in this are including the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, industry representative organisations, media and NGOs. These data are used to inform strategy development, identify priority issues and vulnerable populations, support the development of national and local awareness raising campaigns and develop resources that are delivered by farm advisors to farmers and farm workers. The availability of high quality data that covers all fatalities on farms or associated with farm work means that these initiatives target all vulnerable workers, i.e. not only farmers. The collaborative nature of the farm safety knowledge innovation system in Ireland is a key asset as it insures co-ordination and amplification of key safety messages and heightens awareness of safety initiatives.

6. Farm injury data from Finnish social insurance: Developing evidence-based prevention

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Summary

Farmers and hired agricultural workers in Finland are covered by workers' compensation insurance that keeps records of insured persons and their accidents and occupational diseases. Statistics defined by ESAW are forwarded to Eurostat, including optional data on self-employed farmers. Eurostat uses Labour Force Survey population counts to calculate incidence rates. Farmers Social Insurance Institution (Mela) provides statutory accident insurance coverage to farmers while hired workers are insured similarly by multiple companies. Financial interest to file claims helps reduce under-reporting. Accident and occupational disease data have been instrumental in informing the development of the agricultural safety and health field through policy, research, education, training, and media work. Incidence rates have declined steadily, however, continued persistent preventive work is needed to achieve vision zero and other prevention goals.

Introduction

Regulatory framework. Family farms are generally exempt from occupational health and safety regulations and their enforcement, but hired labour on farms have similar protections as workers in other industries. Farmers as employers must provide a safe and healthy workplace to their employees, and they must provide occupational health services to hired workers on the farm. Occupational health services are provided also to farmers on a voluntary basis, and approximately half of the active farmers have been members, receiving periodic health screenings, farm safety assessments, and consultation. Practically all farmers are covered by mandatory pension and occupational accident insurances. The accident insurance reserves 1.75% of the total insurance costs for prevention. This funding has enabled Farmers Social Insurance Institution (Mela) to have staff, regional advisors, and research funding for health and safety promotion. Mela's accident, occupational disease, and disability pension statistics have been instrumental in informing the development of the agricultural occupational safety and health field in Finland. This report focuses primarily on the self-employed farmers and their non-fatal injuries and occupational diseases that are typically available only in countries that have occupational accident insurance coverage for all self-employed farmers.

Farms

There was a total of 42 271 agricultural and horticultural enterprises in Finland in 2023³². The number of farm operations decreased by 2.6% from the previous year continuing the trend where the number of farms decreases, the farm size increases, and the utilized farm area remains relatively unchanged. The average farm size was 54 hectares of arable land per farm. About 85% of the farms were family-owned and operated; 72% of the farms had crop production as their primary production line, while 20% of farms were classified as livestock farms. About 10% of the farms specialize in dairy, which represents about one third of the economic value of the national agricultural production. Greenhouse enterprises, pig farms, and poultry farms had higher standard output value, but their numbers are quite low. Overall, the number of livestock farms continues to

³² <https://www.luke.fi/en/statistics/structure-of-agricultural-and-horticultural-enterprises/structure-of-agricultural-and-horticultural-enterprises-2023>

decrease while the share of crop production farms increases. Farmers are increasingly engaged in other business activities in addition to basic agriculture. This includes contractual work, processing and direct sales of agricultural products, production of firewood, and tourism³³.

Farm population

The numbers of workers in agriculture are counted differently for different purposes. Data sources include the Farm Structure Survey (FSS), Labour Force Survey (LFS), and social insurance registries.

Farm Structure Survey, Labour Force Survey. According to the 2020 Eurostat agriculture database, based on Farm Structure Survey, a total of 134 157 people worked in agriculture and horticulture in Finland, of whom nearly 70% were farmers, their family members, or partners. About 9 000 farms employed hired labour. About 10 000 hired workers were employed permanently, typically in greenhouses and dairy farms. Short-term labour is common on outdoor horticultural farms. About 20 000 foreign workers are employed in agriculture each year, most on a seasonal basis. The number of annual work units (AWU) in Finnish agriculture was estimated as 56,990 in 2020.³⁴ When back calculating the reference population from the 2021 accident rate provided in Eurostat, the number of workers in agriculture, based on Labour Force Survey, was 66 707.³⁵

Social insurance. The numbers of agricultural entrepreneurs insured by the Farmers Social insurance Institution's MATA insurance, consisted of 45 648 farmers, 1310 farm family members, 478 fishers, 935 reindeer herders, and 3 206 forest growers – 34,578 (71%) men and 14 281 (29%) women for a total of 48 859 insured individual entrepreneurs at the end of year 2023. The number of insured farms was 35 018; smaller than the count based on farm structure survey, partly because of the minimum farm size (5 ha) and income (4 506 E) to be included in the compulsory insurance system. The mandatory insurance applies to those 18 to 68 years of age, working at least 4 months on the farm. Farmers and family members who are not required to have MATA insurance can take it voluntarily.³⁶ The numbers of hired agricultural workers are more difficult to obtain from multiple insurance companies that provide accident insurance coverage for workers. All hired workers including seasonal workers and students must be insured. Youth can work on farms at 14 years of age within limited hours and work duties. At 15 to 17 years of age, they can sign employment contracts and agree to work adult hours in limited work tasks.

Accident data

Data sources. Finland has a well-established social insurance system for farmers that provides retirement, accident insurance, other benefits, and associated data. The farmers work-related MYEL pension insurance started in 1970. It is mandatory for all farms that meet the minimum farm size and income limits. It has definitions for calculating the base income for the farm, typically split evenly between owner-operator spouses. This calculated income is the basis for pension insurance premiums and most benefits for farmers. Those who are required to have the MYEL pension insurance must also have the MATA occupational accident insurance which started in 1982. A specific public-private company established by law, Farmers' Social Insurance Institution (Mela) administers these insurances and other social insurance schemes for self-employed farmers.³⁷ Employees in agriculture are insured similarly, and these social insurance systems produce comprehensive statistics on self-employed and employed agricultural workers' accidents, occupational diseases, disability pensions, and other benefits. The Finnish Workers'

³³ <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-380-746-4>

³⁴ https://doi.org/10.2908/EF_LF_MAIN

³⁵ https://doi.org/10.2908/HSW_N2_01

³⁶ <https://tilastot.mela.fi/aikasarjat?id=4>

³⁷ <https://www.mela.fi/en/>

Compensation Center (TVK) collects data from social insurance systems and Statistics Finland combines and reports them to Eurostat.

Accident frequency. The numbers and rates of accidents in agriculture differ depending on the sources which may use different inclusion criteria. The number of all compensated accidents in 2021 was 3 394 for farmers³⁶ and 818 for employed agricultural workers³⁸. The number of accidents reported in Eurostat (4 or more disability days) for agriculture (NACE code A01) in Finland was 2 630 in 2021, and the incidence rate was 3 943 accidents per 100 000 workers.³⁹ The number of fatal accidents was 6 and the incidence rate was 9 per 100 000 workers. Using MATA data on all compensated accidents and the insured reference population, the annual injury rate has decreased from about 8.5 to 6.5 injuries per 100 farmers during the past three decades. The rates have fluctuated annually due to changes in climate and growing conditions and insurance policies, such as the implementation (1987) and termination (2015) of a premium discount system (no-claims bonus) in MATA insurance.⁴⁰ These changes have affected especially less severe injury claims.⁴¹ Overall, Finland's accident insurance system generates statistics that are based on a well-defined working population and reflect the true incidence of injuries and occupational diseases that involve expenses for medical care, lost work time, and other paid benefits.

Specific accident risks. Insurance data have been used to identify injury and occupational disease risks. Ageing livestock farmers are a particular risk group for occupational injuries, diseases, and disability.⁴² Livestock production, including physical contact with animals, exposes farmers to injuries and illnesses. Repair and maintenance of farm machinery is a particularly risky work activity. The share of machinery-related injuries has increased from 18% to 22% during the past three decades.⁴³ Even though agricultural technologies have developed and working conditions have improved, there are still many smaller farms with outdated buildings and equipment and working environments which expose farmers to injuries and work-related health problems. Modern larger farms may still have remaining risks as well, and musculoskeletal conditions among others are a serious problem.⁴⁴ Disability pension statistics indicate that musculoskeletal diseases and injuries are more frequent, and mental disorders less frequent among farmers compared to the overall working population.⁴⁵ Difficult working postures, heavy lifting and carrying, inadequate recovery, constant hurry, and economic uncertainty as well as older age and female gender are risk factors for musculoskeletal symptoms.⁴⁶

Occupational diseases. The overall occupational disease rate has a downward trend among Finnish farmers⁴³, but agriculture remains a high-risk sector for occupational asthma, rhinitis, contact urticaria or protein contact dermatitis, lateral epicondylitis (tennis elbow) and noise-induced hearing loss.⁴⁷ Also, vole fever (nephropathia epidemica) and cryptosporidiosis are common among farmers. Ammonia and hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) originating from animal waste are health and safety risks for farmers that may cause asthma or lethal poisoning from H₂S.⁴⁸ Technology changes in harvesting and storing hay, straw, wood chips and other organic materials

³⁸ https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/StatFin/StatFin_ttap/statfin_ttap_pxt_129s.px/table/tableViewLayout1/

³⁹ https://doi.org/10.2908/HSW_N2_01

⁴⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajim.20192>

⁴¹ Karttunen, J.P. & Rautiainen, R.H. 2021. Effects of terminating the premium discount incentive on workers' compensation claims among Finnish farmers. Nordic Meeting on Agricultural Occupational Health & Safety, September 6–8, 2021, Skjetlein Grønt Kompetansesenter, Trondheim, Norway.

⁴² <http://hdl.handle.net/10138/42427>

⁴³ <https://tilastot.mela.fi/aikasarjat?id=4>

⁴⁴ <http://hdl.handle.net/10138/42427>

⁴⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1080/1059924X.2015.1042179>

⁴⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140139.2021.1974102>

⁴⁷ TTL, 2022. Occupational diseases and suspected occupational diseases 2018. Finnish Institute of Occupational Health. Helsinki. 82 p.

⁴⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1136/oemed-2020-107323>

at high moisture content resulted in exposure to mold and bioaerosols, which increased the incidence of farmers lung and other respiratory diseases to over 300 cases per year in the 1990s, but then reducing to less than 50 new cases annually in recent years. Better control of musculoskeletal workload remains a priority for farmers, and also foreign farm workers.⁴⁹

Examples of available data

The social insurance systems provide rich data for research and prevention. Each insurance claim is coded for work activity, cause of injury, injured body part, ICD 10 code, incident description (max. 6 lines), lost time due to disability, paid benefits, and numerous other characteristics, including those required by ESAW⁵⁰, and specific national coding. Fatal accidents are coded similarly with additional data on termination of insurance and benefits to survivors. See annex 3 for examples of analytical uses of the insurance data.

Milestone events in agricultural safety and health

The development of health and safety in agriculture in Finland has been influenced by international agreements and standards, overall developments in society and working life,

Figure 13. Notable milestones

structural changes in agriculture towards fewer and larger farm units, and aims to maintain a skilled and able agricultural workforce to provide food security for the nation. A major motivation has been that farmers, like other working populations, can take breaks from arduous work, maintain their livelihood while recovering from injury and illness conditions, retired at a reasonable age, and have farm succession options where younger generations can start their farming career at a relatively young age. Finland has successfully implemented many unique social insurance and support programs for farmers which have been coded into law. Figure 13 shows the timeline of notable milestones in building the infrastructure that farmers' health and safety has been built upon.

Research based on social insurance registries

Data from social insurance registries enable highly sophisticated research approaches. Traditionally research has looked at the frequency, severity, and causes of injuries – focusing on 'what' is the situation with injuries. This **descriptive** information, combined with anecdotal descriptions of injury events is very valuable for education, training, and communication about hazards.

With insurance registries, it is possible compare farmers who have had an injury and those who have managed to avoid them. This **analytical** approach can identify risk factors; what personal

⁴⁹ <https://doi.org/10.13031/JASH.13893>

⁵⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-manuals-and-guidelines/-/KS-RA-12-102>

or farm characteristics increase the risk of injury. This approach is looking for answers, 'why' injuries are happening. This information can be used for targeting interventions to those at high risk; and motivating them with the knowledge about risk factors.

Having continually updated registries of farmers, their farming operation, and social insurance payments and claims and benefits enables many types of **intervention effectiveness** research. Examples include evaluating insurance policy changes by time series analyses; establishing case-control studies or cohorts studies and comparing the claims experience retrospectively and prospectively between study groups. Randomized controlled trials can also be set up by assigning a selected study target group randomly to intervention and control groups, and then managing the intervention and data collection, either with specific data collection instruments or using insurance claims data.

The following figures illustrates how available data have been used to drive policies and practices (Figure 14), and research that has been conducted in collaboration with the Finnish Farmers Social Insurance Institution (Mela), utilizing their data resources (Figure 16). Finally, Figure 15 provides an overview of the advantages when having social insurance-based data available for record keeping and prevention.

Figure 14. Data driving prevention policy and practice

Figure 15. Advantages of social insurance-based system for accident and occupational disease record keeping and prevention

Type of study	Example of conducted study	Ref
Descriptive studies:		
Case study, case series, special topic report, summary of incident descriptions	Descriptive reports: fish farming injuries; automated milking injuries and health risks	51,52
Injury and occupational disease characteristics, trends; coded variables	Characteristics of injuries and occupational diseases, retrospective analysis	53
Economic studies of injury costs	Cost of agricultural injuries and occupational diseases	54
Annual reports	Annual frequency data on insured farmers and their injury, disease, pension, etc. events	36
Analytical studies:		
Cross-sectional study	Multivariable analyses of personal and farm variables as risk factors for injury	55
Case-control study	Dairy producer case control interview study of injury risk factors	56
Cohort study	Comparison of claims between occupational health service members and non-members	55
Intervention effectiveness studies:		
Cross-sectional study	Multivariable analyses of personal and farm variables as risk factors for injury	40,41
Case-control study	Dairy producer case control interview study of injury risk factors	57
Cohort study	Comparison of claims between occupational health service members and non-members	57

Figure 16. Research based on data from Finnish social insurance registries.

⁵¹ <https://doi.org/10.5603/imh.2019.0007>

⁵² <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2016.00147>

⁵³ <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajim.22194>

⁵⁴ https://doi.org/10.1300/J096v10n03_03

⁵⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajim.20688>

⁵⁶ <https://doi.org/10.13031/jash.19.10172>

⁵⁷ <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-380-592-7>

Conclusions

Social insurance systems in Finland provide basic security for self-employed farmers and agricultural workers, enabling them to retire at a usual retirement age and pass on the farm to younger generation when they are still relatively young and able to make long-term investments into modernizing and developing the farm operation. These insurance systems produce valuable process information from the insurance practice; including accurate counts of insured persons, their life and work circumstances, and possible injury, illness, and disability claims they may encounter over their working life. The Finnish accident insurance laws, also for farmers' insurance, require part of the insurance funds to be used for prevention; typically used for education, outreach, media work, and competitive external research project funding. The farmers MATA accident insurance has been established with a clear motivation to prevent injuries and occupational diseases. Over the years, collaboration has been very active between different actors; insurance, research, extension, education, media, farmers and workers organizations and government agencies. With the clear motivation for prevention, it has been possible to utilize the tremendously rich data resources from social insurance databases for research and outreach. While Finland shows a positive model, there is always room for improvement. Data could be published annually in more detail, given Mela's extensive work effort in detailed coding of every claim. Data services, online and by request, could be developed further, so that those who are in the field educating, training, and informing farmers and students would have an easy access to specific data they need. Providing statistics in the English language and presenting them at international venues would be a great service for safety and health personnel in countries that lack similar data resources. Overall, Finland provides a good model for establishing social insurance systems for farmers and utilizing accident, occupational disease and disability data from these systems to inform research and prevention of injuries and illnesses in agriculture.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

In line with key objectives set for the SafeHabitus project, research was undertaken as part of Work Package 3 to improve understanding and awareness of farmer and farm worker health and safety; support the development of policy options that enhance policy and governance frameworks leading to improved working conditions in agriculture; and present case studies of the utility of comprehensive farm fatalities and injuries datasets. These activities contribute to In completing this work, this report contributes key 'Expected Outcomes' that were established by the EU when the call for research proposals on the topic of farm safety and farmer / worker health was published in 2022. In particular, the analysis and recommendations support Outcome 2, *to improve policy and governance frameworks favouring safer working environments*, and Outcomes 4, *to improve health, safety and labour conditions in farming thanks to better performing European and national policy and legal frameworks*. Acting on the recommendations set out below will provide policy stakeholders and policy makers at both EU and national levels with the crucial data that are required to develop strategies and targeted initiatives, similar to those summarised in the case studies from Ireland and Finland, that improve working conditions and enhance the health and safety of all who live and work on farms in the EU.

Study Conclusions

The study reveals significant underreporting of both fatal and non-fatal accidents. The estimated number of 545 fatalities exceeds the average reported number of 315 fatalities by 1.7 times, while the estimated number of 206 000 non-fatal accidents surpasses the average reported number of 127 000 non-fatal accidents by 1.6 times.

The primary reason behind the underreporting of both fatal and non-fatal injuries is the exclusion of self-employed and family workers from reports to Eurostat by member states. While the inclusion/exclusion of these worker categories is voluntary under ESAW regulation, these worker categories form the majority of the labour force of the farms in EU.

Inaccuracies in reference populations, i.e. the denominator used to calculate incident rates, results in either over or underestimated of incidence rates, which are used to compare member states and sectors of the economy. One of the key reasons that reference populations do not match the nominator data is that the denominator comes from a different source. The use of the EU Labour Force Survey is particularly problematic for farming as it excludes most family-workers and seasonal workers. Additional attention is needed to ensure that the reference populations used are appropriate and consistently applied over the time.

Member states with mandatory accident insurance generally have higher-quality accident data. This is because key worker populations, such as self-employed and family workers, are covered by the accident reporting system. Additionally, there are incentives to report accidents, as receiving benefits is tied to reporting.

Recommendations

- **Recommendation 1 - DG AGRI:** Given the critical absence of reliable data to support policy making, we recommend that questions are included in the EU Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN), the EU Farm Structures Survey, and the EU Agriculture Census to identify the number of non-fatal injuries on farms. Each dataset has a unique set of strengths that, when combined, will provide a comprehensive overview of the level of

- **Recommendation 2 - DG AGRI:** We recommend that DG AGRI request, as part of the work planning process for the European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions (Eurofound):
 - The inclusion of questions in the European Working Conditions Surveys (EWCS) that enable the prevalence of occupational injury and ill health, and social sustainability of farming, to be estimated.
 - A special report is published by Eurofound following each EWCS documenting the working conditions of farmers and farm workers and assessing trends over time.

- **Recommendation 3 - DG AGRI:** The analysis of the data provided by the 11 SafeHabitus partners demonstrates that having a social insurance system that provides accident/injury insurance (compensation) for self-employed farmers and family members, in addition to employed workers, is closely associated with the availability of high-quality farm accident data. We recommend that DG AGRI undertake a study to explore the current coverage of farmers, family workers and employees by national social security/protection programmes and assess the feasibility of extending comprehensive occupational injury insurance coverage to self-employed farmers in Member States.

- **Recommendation 4 - Eurostat:** It is recommended that, based on the findings of this study, member states be required to provide data estimating the number of fatal and non-fatal injuries related to farming. It is recognised that this process will take time as it will require legislative changes at the EU level.

- **Recommendation 5 - DG EMPL:** That a working group of the Senior Labour Inspectors Committee (SLIC) be established to focus on improving occupational health and safety of farmers and farm workers. The purpose of the committee will be to:
 - Request regular updates on the number of fatal and non-fatal occupational injuries affecting farmers, family workers and employees.
 - Define common principles of labour inspection in the field of health and safety at work in agriculture and develop methods of assessing the national systems of inspection in relation to those principles.
 - Promote improved knowledge and mutual understanding of the different national systems and practices of labour inspection, the methods and legal frameworks for action.
 - Develop a reliable and efficient system of rapid information exchange between labour inspectorates about health and safety issues in agriculture.
 - Give its opinion on all matters relating to the enforcement by the Member States of EU legislation on health and safety at work in agriculture.
 - Study the possible impact of other Community policies on labour inspection activities relating to health and safety at work and working conditions in agriculture.

Annex 1: Data

Table 5. List and basic statistics of variables used to characterize the land use and people employment in agriculture in European Union countries (n = 27).

Variable	Unit	Source	Year	Mean (median, lower quartile – upper quartile),min – max
Portion of utilised agricultural area in total area	%	ef_m_farmleg; reg_area3	2020	38.8 (43, 30-47), 7-70
Portion of farm labour force in population	%	ef_lf_main; tps00001	2016	5.44 (4.0, 1.0-8.0), 1-31
Ratio of annual work units to farm labour force	-	aact_ali01; ef_lf_main	2016	0.55 (0.50, 0.40-0.70), 0.3-0.9
Portion of permanent crops in UAA	%UAA	ef_m_farmleg	2020	5.60 (2.0, 1.0-6.0), 0-22
Portion of permanent grassland in UAA	%UAA	ef_m_farmleg	2020	30.1 (29.0, 22.0-40.0), 0-75
Portion of areable land in UAA	%UAA	ef_m_farmleg	2020	63.8 (68.0, 51.0-76).0, 25-99
Portion of land owned by natural persons and group holding in UAA	%UAA	ef_m_farmleg	2020	74.2 (81.0, 61.0-92.0), 18-99
Portion of small (<5ha) land units in UAA	%UAA	ef_m_farmleg	2020	8.8 (3.0, 1.0-12.0), 0-79
Portion of field cropping farm type in UAA	%UAA	ef_m_farmleg	2020	41.7 (40.0, 30.0-56.0), 9-71
Portion of horticulture farm type in UAA	%UAA	ef_m_farmleg	2020	1.90 (1.0, 0.0-1.0), 0-22
Portion of husbandry farm type in UAA	%UAA	ef_m_farmleg	2020	36.89 (34, 23-48), 13-84
Portion of crops & livestock farm type in UAA	%UAA	ef_m_farmleg	2020	9.96 (10, 5-13), 2-31
Portion of vineyard farm type in UAA	%UAA	ef_m_farmleg	2020	1.56 (1.0, 0.0-3.0), 0-6
Portion of fruits and citrus farm type in UAA	%UAA	ef_m_farmleg	2020	1.67 (1.0, 0.0-2.0), 0-10
Portion of olive yard farm type in UAA	%UAA	ef_m_farmleg	2020	1.50 (0.0, 0.0-0.0), 0-12
Portion of farm labour force employed on a regular basis in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_main	2016	92.1 (95, 90-97), 63-99

SAFEHABITUS DELIVERABLE 3.1

Variable	Unit	Source	Year	Mean (median, lower quartile – upper quartile), min – max
Portion of sole farm holder in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_main	2016	41.4 (42, 37-50), 16-63
Portion of sole holders' family members working on a regular basis in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_main	2016	26.3 (26, 21-31), 7-50
Portion of non-family farm labour force, employed by the farm on a regular basis in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_main	2016	25.5 (23.0, 13.5-29.5), 3-69
Portion of farm labour force employed on a non-regular basis in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_main	2016	7.2 (5.5, 3-10), 1-18
Portion of women employed on a regular basis in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_main	2016	31.9 (30, 27-39), 14-45
Portion of small (<5ha) land units in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_size	2016	31.7 (25.5, 8.8-53.3), 4-86
Portion of field cropping farm type in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_size	2016	21.4 (21.5, 14.8-29.5), 4-41
Portion of horticulture farm type in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_size	2016	7.4 (5.0, 2.0-9.0), 0-37
Portion of vineyard farm type in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_size	2016	4.2 (3.5, 0.0-6.3), 0-18
Portion of fruits and citrus farm type in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_size	2016	4.5 (3.5, 1.0-6.3), 0-19
Portion of olive yard farm type in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_size	2016	2.41 (0.0, 0.0-1.0), 0-21
Portion of husbandry farm type in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_size	2016	40.8 (38.5, 27.8-48.8), 19-90
Portion of crops & livestock farm type in total AWU	%AWU	ef_lf_size	2016	12.3 (10.0, 4.8-18.5), 2-32
Portion of AWU of legal person owned farms in total AWU	%AWU	ef_m_farmleg	2016	18.8 (12.5, 4.8-26.3), 1-68
Portion of managers with basic training	%	ef_mp_training	2016	26.1 (22, 11-34), 3-91
Portion of managers with practical experience only	%	ef_mp_training	2016	58.3 (54, 47-77), 2-97
Portion of managers with full agricultural training	%	ef_mp_training	2016	15.4 (11, 2-25), 0-53

Annex 2: Research Output associated with health and safety research undertaken by Teagasc researchers (2020 – 2023)

- Brennan, M., Hennessy, T., Dillon, E., & Meredith, D. (2022). Putting social into agricultural sustainability: Integrating assessments of quality of life and wellbeing into farm sustainability indicators. *Sociologia Ruralis*. doi:10.1111/soru.12417
- Brennan, M., Hennessy, T., Meredith, D., & Dillon, E. (2022). Weather, Workload and Money: Determining and Evaluating Sources of Stress for Farmers in Ireland. *Journal of Agromedicine*, 27(2), 132-142. doi:10.1080/1059924X.2021.1988020
- Hammersley, C., Meredith, D., Richardson, N., Carroll, P., & McNamara, J. (2023). Mental health, societal expectations and changes to the governance of farming: Reshaping what it means to be a 'man' and 'good farmer' in rural Ireland. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 63(S1), 57-81. doi:10.1111/soru.12411
- Hammersley, C., Richardson, N., Meredith, D., Carroll, P., & McNamara, J. (2021). "That's Me I am the Farmer of the Land": Exploring Identities, Masculinities, and Health Among Male Farmers' in Ireland. *American Journal of Men's Health*, 15(4). doi:10.1177/15579883211035241
- Hammersley, C., Richardson, N., Meredith, D., Carroll, P., & McNamara, J. (2023). Supporting farmer wellbeing: exploring a potential role for farm advisory staff. *Rural and remote health*, 23(1), 8138. doi:10.22605/RRH8138
- Hammersley, C., Richardson, N., Meredith, D., Carroll, P., & McNamara, J. G. (2022). Supporting farmer wellbeing: exploring a potential role for advisors. *Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*. doi:10.1080/1389224X.2022.2082498
- Matin, S., Sullivan, C. A., Finn, J. A., Ó hUallacháin, D., Green, S., Meredith, D., & Moran, J. (2020). Assessing the distribution and extent of High Nature Value farmland in the Republic of Ireland. *Ecological Indicators*, 108. doi:10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.105700
- McCarthy, J., Meredith, D., & Bonnín, C. (2021). Actor motivations to engage with collaborative agri-environmental policy: An assemblage based exploration. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 87, 88-98. doi:10.1016/j.jrurstud.2021.08.025
- McCarthy, J., Meredith, D., & Bonnín, C. (2022). 'You have to keep it going': Relational values and social sustainability in upland agriculture. *Sociologia Ruralis*. doi:10.1111/soru.12402
- McNamara, J., Kinsella, A., Osborne, A., Blake, C., Meredith, D., & Kinsella, J. (2021). Identifying Farmer Workplace Injury Risk Factors in Ireland Using Farm Accounts Data. *Journal of Agromedicine*, 26(4), 411-419. doi:10.1080/1059924X.2020.1837704
- McNamara, J., Mohammadrezaei, M., Dillon, E., & Meredith, D. (2023). Is presence of children or youth a farm workplace injury risk factor on Irish farms? *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10. doi:10.3389/fpubh.2022.1074673
- Meredith, D., McNamara, J., van Doorn, D., & Richardson, N. (2020). Essential and Vulnerable: Implications of Covid-19 for Farmers in Ireland. *Journal of Agromedicine*, 25(4), 357-361. doi:10.1080/1059924X.2020.1814920
- Meredith, D., Mohammadrezaei, M., McNamara, J., & O'Hora, D. (2022). Towards a Better Understanding of Farm Fatalities: Identification and Estimation of Farming Fatality Rates. *Journal of Agromedicine*. doi:10.1080/1059924X.2022.2113196
- Meredith, D., Mohammadrezaei, M., McNamara, J., & O'Hora, D. (2023). Towards a Better Understanding of Farm Fatalities: Identification and Estimation of Farming Fatality Rates. *Journal of Agromedicine*, 28(2), 239-253. doi:10.1080/1059924X.2022.2113196
- Mohammadrezaei, M., Meredith, D., Flannery, S., Kinsella, J., & McNamara, J. (2023). Does farming experience matter? A comparison of farm health and safety attitudes, perceptions, and intentions of agricultural science students with and without farming experience. *Rural and remote health*, 23(1), 8165. doi:10.22605/RRH8165
- Mohammadrezaei, M., Meredith, D., & McNamara, J. (2022). Beyond Age and Cause: A Multidimensional Characterization of Fatal Farm Injuries in Ireland. *Journal of Agromedicine*. doi:10.1080/1059924X.2022.2116138

- Mohammadrezaei, M., Meredith, D., & McNamara, J. (2022). Subjective norms influence advisors' reluctance to discuss farm health and safety. *Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*. doi:10.1080/1389224X.2022.2125410
- Mohammadrezaei, M., Meredith, D., & McNamara, J. (2023). Beyond Age and Cause: A Multidimensional Characterization of Fatal Farm Injuries in Ireland. *Journal of Agromedicine*, 28(2), 277-287. doi:10.1080/1059924X.2022.2116138
- Mohammadrezaei, M., Meredith, D., McNamara, J., Kinsella, J., & Flannery, S. (2023). Do social influences, awareness, or experience matter? Toward a better understanding of Farm-related Injury Risk Perception among agricultural science college students in Ireland. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11. doi:10.3389/fpubh.2023.1076332
- Mohammadrezaei, M., Meredith, D., & McNamara, J. (2024). Counting Farm Injuries and Fatalities: An Assessment of Irish Occupational Health and Safety Surveillance Data Systems. *Journal of Agromedicine*, 29(2), 289-296. doi:10.1080/1059924X.2024.2317862
- O'Connor, T., Kinsella, J., McNamara, J., O'Hora, D., & Meredith, D. (2021). Learning through design using collaborative Intervention Mapping with acceptability evaluation: the case of a group-based farm safety intervention. *Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 27(3), 403-420. doi:10.1080/1389224X.2020.1858889
- O'Connor, T., Meredith, D., McNamara, J., O'Hora, D., & Kinsella, J. (2021). Farmer Discussion Groups Create Space for Peer Learning about Safety and Health. *Journal of Agromedicine*, 26(2), 120-131. doi:10.1080/1059924X.2020.1720882
- O'Driscoll, J., Meredith, D., Crowley, F., Doran, J., O'Shaughnessy, M., & Zimmermann, J. (2022). The spatiotemporal dimension of population change in Ireland: visualisation of growth and shrinkage in Irish Electoral Divisions (1986–2016). *Journal of Maps*, 18(3), 551-557. doi:10.1080/17445647.2022.2052766
- O'Connor, T., Kinsella, J., O'Hora, D., McNamara, J., & Meredith, D. (2022). Safer tomorrow: Irish dairy farmers' self-perception of their farm safety practices. *Journal of Safety Research*, 82, 450-458. doi:10.1016/j.jsr.2022.07.012
- O'Reilly, A., Meredith, D., Foley, R., & McCarthy, J. (2023). Continuity, change and new ways of being: An exploratory assessment of farmer's experiences and responses to public health restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic in a rural Irish community. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 63(S1), 95-115. doi:10.1111/soru.12424
- Surendran, A., McSharry, J., Meade, O., Bligh, F., McNamara, J., Meredith, D., & O'Hora, D. (2023). Increasing Machine-Related Safety on Farms: Development of an Intervention Using the Behaviour Change Wheel Approach. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 20(5394). doi:https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20075394
- Van Doorn, D., Richardson, N., Meredith, D., Blake, C., & McNamara, J. (2022). Study protocol: Evaluation of the 'real-world' Farmers Have Hearts – Cardiovascular Health Program. *Preventive Medicine Reports*, 30. doi:10.1016/j.pmedr.2022.102010

Annex 3: Examples of analytical uses of the Finnish insurance data

Figure 17 shows the number of injured farmers from 1991 to 2020. The number of farmers has reduced from about 170 000 in 1991 to about 60 000 in 2020. Nearly 1/3 of the farmers have been female during this period. Figure 18 shows the injury rate per 100 farmers. The incidence rate has decreased gradually from 8.5 to 6.5 injuries per hundred workers. Figure 19 shows the share of machinery injuries increasing from 18% to 22% reflecting the increased farm size and use of technology. Figure 20 shows great numbers of farmer's lung cases in the 1990's, reducing to relatively few in recent years due to technology changes, education, and better personal protection. Figure 21 shows the distribution of injuries by their severity. For each fatal injury there is approximately 500 non-fatal injuries, which is in accordance with the well-established 'Heinrich's pyramid' severity structure.⁵⁸ Figure 22 shows the main causes of accidents. The working environment, animals, and structures are prominent injury causes, followed by machinery and working motions. Figure 23 shows the distribution of injuries by work activity, and Figure 24 shows injury risk factors from multivariable regression analyses, and Figure 26 shows accident rates by municipality. Figure 25 shows insurance costs per farmer in the early years of the MATA insurance by type of paid benefit. Medical expenses are only about 1/5th of the total costs while lost time compensation represents more than half of the costs. Twenty percent of the most serious cases represent about 80% of the total injury costs in this system.⁵⁹

Figure 17. Number of insured farmers, 1991-2020

⁵⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2017.09.005>

⁵⁹ https://doi.org/10.1300/J096v10n03_03

Figure 18. Accident rate per 100 farmers, 1991-2020

Figure 19. Share of machinery accidents, 1991-2020

Figure 20. Number of occupational diseases by cause

Figure 21. Relative number of non-fatal accidents per one fatality case in nine compensated lost work time categories. 2002 MATA data

Figure 22. Accidents and occupational disease causes 1991-2020

Figure 23. Percentage of accidents by work activity 1991-2020, n = 220,445

Figure 24. Selected risk factors for injury (Odds Ratios) MATA data 2002, n = 94,115

Figure 25. MATA insurance costs per insured farmer by type of benefit. 1982-1999

National average 5,2 %
(Number of compensated injury
and occupational disease cases
per 100 insured farmers)

Incident rate (n of municipalities)

- < 4 % (122 municipalities)
- 4 % - 5,2 % (58 municipalities)
- 5,2 % - 8 % (80 municipalities)
- yli 8 % (50 municipalities)

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Figure 26. MATA-incident rates by municipality, 2020

Annex 4: Milestone events in agricultural safety and health in Finland

The development of health and safety in agriculture in Finland has been greatly influenced by participating in the development and implementing international agreements and standards as well as developing advanced programs and coding them into law. Following are some notable programs that have been implemented in chronological order.

1923 (ILO C011, Right of association, Ag.), 1950 (ILO C012 Workmen's comp., Ag.), 1968 (ILO 129, Inspections, Ag.), 2003 (ILO 184 SH in Agriculture). Finland has ratified ILO conventions related to agricultural safety and health in agriculture. These have provided international perspective and support to meet and exceed high standards in national legislation and programs.

1946-2018 VAKOLA Agricultural machinery testing. VAKOLA had a major role in conducting ISO, OECD, and other test to ensure safety of ag machinery before they come to market. This included testing of ROPS structures and functioning of equipment in cold conditions. The testing is currently done by manufacturers, and VAKOLA ended operation in 2018.

1969 ROPS required on new tractors. Finland was one of the first countries to make tractor rollover protection structure (ROPS) and cab mandatory on new tractors. This requirement has gradually reduced the number of rollover fatalities towards zero per year.

1970 MYEL pension insurance. The MYEL work-related pension system was implemented to enable retirement options to farmers who in many cases had chronic health conditions from heavy agricultural work or military service in WWII. The pension system enabled structural change towards fewer larger sustainable farm units, and earlier transfer of farm ownership to younger generation.

1974 Relief worker services. Farm relief system was implemented in response to the physical and mental strain in animal husbandry, particularly to female farmers. This service provides a relief worker to do necessary animal care work during annual vacation (currently 26 days), maternity, or recovery from an injury or occupational disease.

1974 Kuopio Regional Institute of Occupational Health (agriculture) (KATTIL). The establishment of KATTIL provided a critical resource to investigate agricultural work exposures and health conditions, develop diagnostic methods to agricultural occupational diseases, and developing, testing, and implementing the agricultural occupational health service model.

1979 Agricultural occupational health services (OHS). OHS has been the primary national investment in the prevention of occupational injury and illness in agriculture in Finland. OHS includes registration, health screening, on-farm health and safety assessment, and consultation. The services are conducted periodically, every 3-4 years. About half of the farmers have been members since mid 1980s. Membership requires an annual fee, and members receive a 20% discount in their MATA accident insurance premiums.

1982 MATA accident insurance. The MATA farmers' accident insurance is mandatory for most farmers. It provides compensation for work-related accidents and occupational diseases. Insured farmers have coverage for short term illness compensation, and they can take a voluntary accident insurance for leisure time. The details of the insurance system and data that it produces have been discussed earlier.

2016 Sacurima COST Action. Finland has developed capacity for agricultural safety and health research while national funding has diminished. The Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke) took the lead in the Safety Culture and Risk Management in Agriculture (Sacurima) COST Action to develop a network of experts and institutions across Europe to facilitate future collaboration in the agricultural safety and health field.

2017 Support the farmer program. Farmers' Social Insurance Institution (Mela) administers a program that provides work ability consultation and vouchers for therapy by health professionals. Mela has a regional network of trained providers who serve as the initial contact in situations like coping with stress, relationships, business challenges, or family situations. Services may include therapy for personal health, partner and family relationships, psychologist, psychiatrist, or occupational coaching.

2023 SafeHabitus. Luke and Savonia agricultural college have joined the SafeHabitus project and they have a major role in Work packages dealing with communities of practice and agricultural accident statistics and risk management programs.

Annex 5: Regarding use of the term ‘Accident’ in SafeHabitus D3.1.

The term ‘Accident’ as used in ESAW stands for European Statistics on **Accidents** at Work. In their methodology, an "accident" refers to an event—a discrete occurrence during work that leads to physical or mental harm. Accordingly, the term ‘Accident’ is used throughout this report when it refers to the occurrence or ‘incident’ that lead to physical or mental harm.

However, it should be noted, that variation occurs in use of the term ‘accident’ in scientific literature. A number of peer reviewed occupational health and safety publications regard the description ‘accident’ as unacceptable as it implies: ‘a chance occurrences which cannot be prevented’ which they consider gives a conflicting perception i.e. ‘accidents’ can be prevented. Such publications instead use the term ‘injury’. The terms accident and injury have been used interchangeably within the report in reference to a medical condition resulting from a fatal or non-fatal incident.

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